

Theory of time constant correlation of a porous bed thermal energy storage tank - Experimental and numerical proof of concept

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ABSTRACT

Analytical modeling of energy systems is used to estimate the potential of the system, but several simplifications used lead to progressive deviations from the actual potential. Thermal Energy Storage tanks are most often treated as black boxes, by limiting their characteristics to their energy efficiency and basic capacity only. This paper introduces the theory of a time constant that correlates the basic parameters of a porous bed heat storage tank and allows the charge level of the tank to be determined during the charging stage. The correlation for the time constant has a coefficient that has been fully validated both experimentally and numerically for a wide range of parameters. Coefficient values for different precision test runs have been indicated, and the prediction deviation using the time constant does not exceed a value of 5 % relative to the actual results. The proposed methodology for the analytical model of the tank accurately represents the cyclic operation of the heat storage tank. It has also been shown that the cyclic operation of the heat storage tank fixes the charge level in the range of 0.16–0.79. The methodology presented can be used to modelling and designing energy systems with heat storage.

1. Introduction

Shift toward clean energy requires application of energy storage on different scales. Their implementation as integrators of renewable energy sources (RES) with the power grid will allow for an increase in the daily utilization of RES by matching electricity generation with demand from end users. The breadth of renewable energy implementation is also leading to improvements in technology and lower construction costs - according to IRENA's 2023 report, the cost of building 1 kW of photovoltaic panels decreased from \$5124 to \$876 in years 2010–2022, a decrease of 83 % [1]. The process of decarbonization of the power industry is leading to a reduction in the flexibility of the electricity system, although various alternative paths are being proposed. One of such ways is Coal-to-Nuclear transition, which involves replacing coal-fired boilers with nuclear reactors [2,3], allowing the energy source to remain controllable [4]. It has been proposed that the nuclear reactor will operate at a constant load, and the adjustment of electricity production will be done by integrating the nuclear and steam sections using Thermal Energy Storage (TES). Increasing the flexibility of energy systems and their successful integration into the power grid can be achieved through heat storage. Such solutions are used, among others, in

concentrated solar power (CSP) systems, where heat can be accumulated in both fluids (for example, molten salts [5]) and a porous bed [6]. The study of flows through porous beds is relevant to many technologies. Waniczek et al. [7], presented the concept of utilising a porous bed heat storage tank as an integral component of an adiabatic compressed air energy storage system (A-CAES). The primary objective of their research was to examine the challenges associated with the design of a high-pressure heat storage tank and to illustrate the influence of its slenderness on exergy efficiency. Furthermore, the porous bed heat storage tank was included in the A-CAES system that was examined in the ADELE project [8]. The high-pressure ground-based heat storage tank was designed with a height of 50 m and a diameter of 24 m. The study showed that the construction of such a tank would account for a significant part of the investment, as the high pressure and high heat storage temperature necessitated expensive tank wall construction techniques. Zanganeh et al. [9] presented a pilot-scale packed bed heat storage tank. The heat storage was part of an energy storage system based on an industrial solar power plant. Porous beds are not only used as heat storage - Katla et al. [10] presented a system concept for the production of synthetic natural gas (SNG), where the catalyst fill was a ruthenium-aluminum bed. Otitoju et al. [11] discussed a rotating porous

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bed used to absorb CO₂ from a gas turbine system. Although heat storage in porous beds is the most common concept, the degree of accuracy of their modeling varies significantly. Experimental and numerical analyses are usually performed on only laboratory-scale test stands [12–14]. System analyses of larger systems using TES are mainly limited to parameters such as the energy efficiency of the tank [15,16]. Roos and Haselbacher, in their review of analytical models of advanced adiabatic energy storage systems in compressed air, pointed out that Thermal Energy Storage, even in accurate modelling of system behavior, are often treated as “black boxes” without taking into account changes in their parameters during operational time [17], which can lead to unrealistic assumptions about the durations of the charging and discharging stages. Simplifications were also used by Courtois et al. [18] where the heat exchange with the TES did not bring pressure drops in the heat transfer medium, and charging and discharging took place at steady state. To date, experimental studies of porous-filled heat storage tanks have mainly covered the range of different storage materials and heat storage tank configurations. Schwarzmayr et al. [19] investigated a heat storage tank that was filled with rock material. The diameter of the tank was variable along its length, which had a direct impact on the operational performance of the tank. Kothari et al. [20] performed an experimental study of a tank more than 5 m high, and successfully validated a numerical model. Cascetta et al. [21,22] presented experimental and numerical studies on an alumina-filled heat tank with a diameter of 0.58 m. Calderon-Vasquez and Cardemil [23] numerically investigated different shapes of porous bed heat storage tanks and validated the model based on experimental results. Their results show that short charging periods and long discharging periods increase the energy efficiency of the TES tank. All these studies have indicated that the process of temperature rise of the storage material. In a porous-filled tank can be accurately simulated numerically, allowing the numerical modelling of extensive energy storage systems. Ochmann et al. [24] presented a methodology for a numerical model of an adiabatic compressed air energy storage system, where the heat storage tank was modeled to a one-dimensional temperature distribution in a simplified approach. The paper presented herein constitutes a continuation of the authors’ experimental and numerical studies [25,26] to determine universal properties of heat storage tanks aiming at the upgrades of the models of TES and energy storage systems.

The main novelty of this paper is the determination of a correlation of the time constant of Thermal Energy Storage with porous bed filling, whereby it is possible to determine the duration of the charging stage of the tank, in which the increment of accumulated heat is constant. Once this time is exceeded, there is a rapid increase in the exhaust loss from the TES tank. The time constant is used in the proposed analytical equation that describes cyclic operation of TES in terms of charge level as a function of time. The proposed methodology is therefore a significant upgrade over previously used methods for the analytical solution of the behavior of heat storage tanks cooperating with energy storage systems [27–29]. Furthermore, the elaborated methodology can provide design support for the initial assumptions of the operation of energy storage systems.

The determined correlation for the time constant was verified both experimentally and numerically as part of the research work, taking into account the boundary conditions according to in-house experiment. This arrangement reduced the computational inaccuracy with a one-dimensional temperature recording of the accumulation material. Furthermore, an extensive multivariate analysis was performed for different characteristic parameters of both the TES tank and the heat transfer fluid (HTF). The multivariate analysis included the study of different TES sizes - both in terms of diameter and height - so that a wide range of heat accumulator volumes and slendernesses were investigated. In addition, a number of different heat accumulator materials were investigated, which were characterised by a wide range of specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity values. On this basis, the coefficient used in the correlation per time constant was empirically defined. The

accuracy of the correlation was assessed using the mean squared error and it was shown that both the correlation and the methodology for determining the time course of the filling of the heat transfer tank satisfactorily simulated the expected values.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental test stand

The experimental procedure was carried out on the in-house laboratory stand. A detailed description of the laboratory stand as well as the measurement procedure was discussed in the previous papers [25,26]. The thermal storage tank system has so far been successfully used as the basis for studies focused on TES itself as well as a part of full-scale electricity storage systems. The heat storage tank made of stainless steel is filled with a basalt bed, with an average particle diameter of 16 mm. The basalt bed fills the reservoir with a height of 3 m and an inner diameter of 0.213 m. The novelty concerning previous research conducted on this stand is the acquisition of full temperature characteristics of the heat storage charging process for the case without thermal insulation (Fig. 1 (a)) and with thermal insulation with a thickness of 50 mm and a thermal conductivity coefficient of 0.038 W/mK (Fig. 1 (b)). This makes it possible to determine individual dependencies for a slender heat storage tank.

The temperature of the basalt is measured using 10 resistance temperature sensors Pt100 Class A steel sheathed with a temperature measurement range of $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} - 550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which are located along the symmetry axis of the heat storage tank at an equal distance $x = 0.33\text{ m}$ from each other. The air temperature at the tank’s inlet and outlet is also measured - the corresponding resistance temperature sensors are placed directly at the inlet and outlet of the heat storage tank in the connection chambers. The inlet chamber can be seen in Fig. 1 (b) as an uninsulated element on top of the storage tank. The pressure drop Δp value of the air flowing through the rock bed was also measured using a differential pressure sensor. Measurements were performed with the following rules:

- A temperature of about $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is maintained in the laboratory room. The air for the system is taken from the room volume, while the exhaust air from the storage tank is directed outside the room preventing changes in room conditions. There are no devices installed in the room to force the movement of ambient air, so the external surface of the storage tank exchanges heat with the environment by free convection.
- The air supplied to the tank has an atmospheric pressure. The side channel blower with a 7.5 kW motor produces the overpressure necessary to overcome the linear and local resistance of the laboratory bench. The air is heated using a 17 kW Lester model LE 10000 electric heater to a predetermined temperature.
- Each time before the experimental campaign, the volume flow rate of air is determined, as well as the expected temperature at the inlet to the storage tank. The air is heated using an electric heater. Due to heat loss to the environment and the need to heat the elements of the laboratory bench, the inlet temperature to the tank reaches a temperature close to the expected temperature with a delay. The delay is individual for each measurement series and depends on the airflow and the value of the expected temperature.
- At the end of a given experimental series, there was a regime of at least a 3-day interval during which the rock bed was cooled by a forced stream of unheated air. The rock bed was cooled until the difference between the temperature reading of the rock bed and the ambient temperature was less than 5 K.
- Experiments were conducted up to steady state, which was defined as the point at which temperature measurements along the tank’s symmetry axis indicate a no temperature rise defined as $< 0.5\text{ K}$ over 10 min for each of the resistive temperature sensors.

Fig. 1. (a) TES tank without thermal insulation; (b) TES tank with 50 mm thick thermal insulation.

The measurement procedure consists of several steps. In the first step, the valve configuration is changed depending on the phase. If the charging phase is investigated, the heated air blows from the top of the stand, otherwise, cold air flows from the bottom in the discharging phase. In the second step, the compressor is launched and set on a demanded mass flow rate. Subsequently, the data acquisition system is initialised to collect the experimental data, process it, and control the test stand. In the case of the charging phase, the electric heater is

launched to heat the air to a demanded temperature level and the measurement data can be collected.

Fig. 2 (a) presents a simplified scheme of the laboratory stand. The valve configuration makes it possible to investigate the charging and discharging stages of the heat storage tank from both the top and bottom. The reversible operation of the heat accumulator corresponds to the proposed concept of operating the TES accumulator in the mine shaft space [30,31]. Fig. 2 (b) shows the distribution and designations of the

Fig. 2. (a) Laboratory stand diagram; (b) schematic of the arrangement of measuring devices on the TES tank.

resistance temperature sensors and the location of the measurement of the pressure drop of air Δp flowing through the storage tank, which is performed with a differential pressure transducer with a maximum range of 10 kPa. The maximum air pressure is also measured on a measuring orifice made of acid-resistant steel (Cr-Ni).

The determination of thermophysical parameters (thermal conductivity coefficient, specific heat capacity) of basalt, which was used as a heat accumulator in the TES tank, was also experimentally studied. For the study, the C-Therm TCi Thermal Conductivity Analyzer was used, which allows testing of the thermal conductivity coefficient in the range from 0 W/(m·K) to 500 W/(m·K) at temperatures from $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [32]. The measurements required the adaptation of rock material samples according to the requirements of the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) sensor, i.e., making an incision in the samples to obtain a maximum flat contact surface between the sensor and the element of about 15 mm in diameter. During the experimental tests, the contact material between the sensor and the rock element was distilled water. Measurements of the conductivity coefficient of rock were made at ambient temperature and pressure. The accuracy and precision of the device are less than 5 % and 1 %, respectively, at temperatures from $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The obtained results of the thermal conductivity coefficient were matched with the existing correlations [33] for basalt grit. Based on the obtained values of the material's effusivity, it was also possible to analytically determine the specific heat capacity of the rock at ambient temperature. The uncertainty of temperature measurement for resistance thermometers was calculated using the documentation provided by the manufacturer of the measuring equipment [34]. The flow rate was measured using an orifice. In this case, documentation for a given type of device was also used to calculate the measurement uncertainty [35]. The uncertainties for both measured quantities are presented graphically along with the presentation of the obtained measurement results carried out at the laboratory station.

2.2. Analytical model concept

The concept of the time constant of the porous bed heat storage tank was based on experimental observations indicating that the theoretical inflection point of the linear increase in the charge level of the tank occurs around 0.70 of the maximum value under the given temperature conditions of the heat storage. This phase, called here accumulation stage, is characterized by minimal exhaust loss and, therefore, exergy losses. Above the charge level of 0.70 filling stage occurs. In this phase a significantly slower charging pace is observed and the exhaust loss is increasing. Charge level is defined as:

$$\theta = \frac{E_{\text{stored}}}{E_{\text{stored}}^{\text{max}}} \quad (1)$$

where E_{stored} is defined as the energy stored in the heat tank during the tank's operation and $E_{\text{stored}}^{\text{max}}$ is defined as maximum energy that can be stored by the heat tank at the determined maximum HTF temperature. Fig. 3 shows the idealized course of the charge level during the charging stage of the heat storage tank, with a description of the characteristic values.

The accumulation stage is defined as the time during which the accumulation of the heat supplied in the rock bed of the tank is the dominant process. An almost linear increase in the value of the tank charge level θ is observed. Once the $\tau_{0.70}$, which is determined by the proposed correlation, is exceeded, the increase in the degree of charge level θ slows down and the filling stage of the tank begins. During this stage, an intense increase in the outlet air temperature is observed. Due to the temperature gradient inside the tank, the value of the heat flux between the HTF and the rock material decreases. The value of the heat loss rate to the environment determines the real value of θ achieved, however, both experimentally and numerically it has been shown that θ reaches values between 0.94 and 0.98. It takes a couple of times longer

Fig. 3. Scheme of division of the charging stage of a heat storage tank into an accumulation stage and a filling stage.

to reach this value from $\theta = 0.70$ than the stage from $\theta = 0$ to $\theta = 0.70$.

A significant increase in the temperature of the outlet fluid is not preferable in compressed air energy storage systems, for example, as it also results in a temperature increase in the compressed air reservoir. In order to determine the universal time constant of a tank with a specific volume V , a dimensional analysis was carried out according to Equation (2):

$$\frac{\tau_{0.70}}{V} = f(\rho_{bd}, cp_r, cp_f, \dot{m}_f) \quad (2)$$

In the analysis, it was assumed that the accumulation process depended on the flow parameters as well as the physical properties of the bed material and heat transfer fluid (HTF). The heat conduction was omitted since convection was the dominant factor determining heat transfer conditions. The amount of energy that can be stored in the accumulation material depends on volumetric heat capacity $\rho_{bd}cp_r$, therefore, it had to be included in the dimensional analysis. This parameter depended on the bulk density of material ρ_{bd} and specific heat capacity at constant pressure cp_r . Bulk density was calculated based on the rock density and porosity of a bed according to the formula $\rho_{bd} = \rho_r \cdot (1 - \epsilon)$. The enthalpy flow rate carried by the heat transfer fluid depended on its specific heat capacity at constant pressure cp_f and mass flow rate \dot{m}_f . Based on the analysis, a correlation was proposed for the time constant $\tau_{0.70}$ per defined volume of the heat storage tank V , which is presented in Equation (3):

$$\frac{\tau_{0.70}}{V} = C \cdot \frac{\rho_{bd}}{\dot{m}_f} \left(\frac{cp_r}{cp_f} \right) \quad (3)$$

where C is an empirically defined coefficient. Determining the value of the time constant of a heat tank of a given volume V determines the time of the charging stage, where the value of the charge level θ is equal to 0.70.

The physical meaning of the correlation presented in Equation (3) is to determine the overcharge of the energy input to the heat tank in order to achieve the required charge level. This overcharge is mainly due to the varying intensity of the heat transfer between the HTF and the rock material, the exhaust loss, heat loss to the environment, heat accumulation in the walls and insulation of the heat storage tank. Due to the lack of accumulation of all input energy, the C coefficient for a value of $\theta = 0.70$ will always be greater than 0.70. Based on the determined time constant of the heat tank, it is possible to analytically determine an approximate time course of the θ -value according to the Equation (4):

$$\theta(t) = \alpha \cdot \frac{e^{\beta \cdot t'} - e^{-\beta \cdot t'}}{e^{\beta \cdot t'} + e^{-\beta \cdot t'}} = \alpha \cdot \tanh(\beta \cdot t') \quad (4)$$

where the coefficients α , β , γ depend on the value of $\tau_{0.70}$. Determining the course of the θ value also makes it possible to determine the course of the HTF pressure drop value Δp at time t , which can be directly used in the analytical modelling of systems using Thermal Energy Storage with porous rock filling. An illustrative decision-making scheme is presented in Fig. 4.

An energy efficiency parameter η_{TES} was used to evaluate TES tank operations. The definition is presented in Equation 5

$$\eta_{TES} = \frac{\int_0^{t_c} \dot{m}_{HTF} \cdot c_{p_f} \cdot (T_{in}^d - T_{out}^d) dt}{\int_0^{t_d} \dot{m}_{HTF} \cdot c_{p_f} \cdot (T_{in}^c - T_{out}^c) dt} \quad (5)$$

where \dot{m}_{HTF} is the HTF mass flow, T_{in}^c and T_{out}^c are the inlet and outlet temperatures, respectively, of the HTF during the charging stage, T_{in}^d and T_{out}^d are the inlet and outlet temperatures of the HTF during the discharging stage, t_c and t_d are the duration of the charging and discharging stages respectively.

The value of the pressure drop of HTF flowing through a porous filled heat tank can be calculated using the Ergun equation [36]:

$$\frac{|\Delta p|}{L} = \frac{150 \cdot \mu_f \cdot (1 - \varepsilon)^2}{D_p^2} \cdot v_\infty + \frac{1.75 \cdot \rho_f \cdot (1 - \varepsilon)}{D_p} \cdot \frac{v_\infty^2}{\varepsilon^3} \quad (6)$$

where v_∞ is the HTF superficial velocity in packed bed, μ_f is the air dynamic viscosity, D_p is the particle diameter. Superficial velocity in packed bed is defined as:

$$v_\infty = \frac{\dot{m}_{HTF}}{\rho_f \cdot A_{TES}} \quad (7)$$

where A_{TES} is the TES cross-sectional area. Physical velocity in packed bed is defined as:

$$v_{pb} = \frac{v_\infty}{\varepsilon} \quad (8)$$

The use of time constant theory and the modelling of the TES tank charge level enables.

- A more accurate estimation of the required volume of the TES tank in relation to the assumed parameters of the energy storage system, especially from the perspective of the heat flux supplied to the heat storage,

Fig. 4. Flow chart of the proposed methodology.

- Analysis of the synchronous, cyclic operation of the energy storage system including determination of the duration of the charging and discharging phases,
- Analytical comparison of different heat tank configurations in terms of accumulation material and packed bed porosity,
- Obtaining pressure drop values Δp that vary during the operation of the energy storage system, which directly affects the performance of other system components

In order to validate the proposed correlation, a series of experimental tests were carried out on different laboratory bench configurations (Fig. 1) with varying mass flow rate and maximum temperature of air. In addition, a multivariate sensitivity analysis was performed using an experimentally validated numerical model in ANSYS Fluent.

2.3. Numerical model

Numerical analyses were carried out in ANSYS Fluent. The numerical model was extended to include a porous zone model. The thermophysical parameters of the gas, accumulation material and steel and thermal insulation used were made temperature dependent. The momentum, energy and mass conservation laws constituted the set of governing equations. Porous Zone model extends the momentum loss equation to the following form [37]:

$$\frac{\partial(\epsilon\rho\vec{v})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\epsilon\rho\vec{v}) = -\epsilon\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\epsilon\vec{\tau}) + \epsilon\vec{B}_f - \left(\frac{\mu}{\alpha} + \frac{C_2\rho}{2}|\vec{v}|\right)\vec{v} \quad (9)$$

where \vec{v} is the superficial velocity of air in packed bed area, p is the pressure of air, $\vec{\tau}$ is the stress tensor, \vec{B}_f are the external body forces and μ is the viscosity of air.

The heat transfer process defined by time-varying values was modeled using a Non-Equilibrium Thermal Model, which results in separate conservation equations solved for both the solid and fluid zones. Energy conservation equation for fluid zone is defined as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\epsilon\rho_f E_f) + \nabla \cdot (\vec{v}(\rho_f E_f + p)) = \nabla \cdot (\epsilon k_f \nabla T_f - (h_f J_f) + (\vec{\tau} \cdot \vec{v})) + h_{fs} A_{fs} (T_s - T_f) \quad (10)$$

where E_f is the total fluid energy, k_f and T_f is the fluid heat conductivity coefficient and its temperature, h_{fs} is the convective heat transfer coefficient between fluid and solid material, A_{fs} is the interfacial area density between the fluid and the solid, T_s is the temperature of solid material.

Energy conservation equation for solid zone is defined as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}((1 - \epsilon)\rho_s E_s) = \nabla \cdot ((1 - \epsilon)k_s \nabla T_s) + h_{fs} A_{fs} (T_f - T_s) \quad (11)$$

where E_s is the total solid material energy, k_s is the conductivity coefficient,

The value of the heat transfer coefficient h_{fs} is determined by solving the correlation on the Nusselt number. The equation was implemented into ANSYS Fluent using the User Defined Function (UDF), which allows the equation to be solved dynamically at each time step and the coefficient value to change locally. The correlation used on the Nusselt number is presented in Equation (12) [38,39]

$$Nu = 2 + 1.1 \cdot Re^{0.6} \cdot Pr^{1/3} = \frac{h_{fs} \cdot D_p}{k_f} \quad (12)$$

The computational domain included both the porous bed area and the steel tank walls, as well as the thermal insulation area, depending on the case studied. The axisymmetry of the heat tank was employed to reduce the computational domain to a two-dimensional surface.

2.4. Assumptions for experiment and numerical multivariate analysis

The experimental tests were carried out on the laboratory bench in two configurations (with and without thermal insulation) as indicated in Fig. 1. According to the experimental plan, the expected maximum inlet air temperature and the expected air mass flow rate were determined for each measurement series. Due to the different intensity of heat transfer and heating of the bench elements - the maximum inlet air temperature actually achieved was lower than the expected temperature and reached with a certain delay. The range of air temperatures and airflows tested, as well as the laboratory bench parameters, are presented in Table 1.

Numerical studies with time-varying boundary conditions based on experimental data took into account the recorded air mass flow and temperature over time. Implementation of time-varying boundary conditions was performed using external data tables imported into ANSYS Fluent. Due to the limited variability of key parameters during the experiment, an extensive multivariate analysis was performed. As a part of the numerical multivariate analysis, calculations were performed for a wide range of variables defining the heat tank. Variations were mainly related to the determined mass flow rate, the dimensions of the heat storage tank and the material that forms the energy accumulator. The numerical studies used materials that have a wide range of thermo-physical parameters and are proposed as accumulation materials, i.e. basalt, sandstone, granite and alumina. Their thermophysical parameters were made temperature dependent according to the source data. The porosity of the porous bed was also varied, which consequently led to changes in the mass of the bed, as well as the maximum amount of energy that could be accumulated. Experiments performed by Beasley and Clark [40] and Beavers et al. [41] examined the dependence of the porosity of a packed bed on the relation of the diameter of the tank D to the diameter of the rock material elements D_p . For values of the parameter $\varphi = D/D_p$ from 5 to 30, the obtained porosity value ϵ ranges from about 0.37 to 0.43. The laboratory stand discussed in this article is characterized by a value of the parameter $\varphi = 13.3$, and the calculated porosity is 0.38, which corresponds to the results obtained in previous studies. The ranges of values tested are presented in Table 2.

3. Results

3.1. Validation of numerical model

The validation of the numerical model included all the experimental series carried out. The temperature and mass flow boundary conditions were time-dependent according to the experimental data and implemented as data tables into ANSYS Fluent. In addition, each experimental series had an individual ambient temperature condition, with the initial basalt temperature distribution implemented using the UDS equation and dependent on the position along the tank symmetry axis. Fig. 5 (a) and (b) present exemplary results of the temperature distribution of the

Table 1
Assumptions for experimental studies.

Item	Value	Unit
Desired air temperature at inlet of TES	323.15, 343.15, 363.15	K
Desired air mass flow at inlet of TES	0.032, 0.049, 0.067, 0.084	kg/s
Desired air mass flux at inlet of TES	0.85, 1.32, 1.78, 2.23	kg/(s·m ²)
Desired superficial air velocity at inlet of TES	0.82–2.43	m/s
Desired physical air velocity at inlet of TES	2.16–6.38	m/s
Diameter of packed bed particles	0.016	m
TES tank diameter	0.219	m
TES tank height	3.0	m
Storage material	Basalt	–
Heat transfer fluid	Air	–
Average porosity of packed bed	0.38	–

Table 2
Assumptions for numerical studies [22,33].

Item	Value	Unit
Air mass flow	0.03–0.07	kg/s
Air mass flux	0.84–1.96	kg/(s·m ²)
Superficial air velocity	0.33–2.06	m/s
Physical air velocity	0.78–5.42	m/s
Diameter of TES tank	0.213–0.349	m
Height of TES tank	0.55–4.50	m
Porosity of packed bed	0.36–0.42	–
Specific heat capacity of accumulation material	660–920	J/(kg·K)
Density of accumulation material	2640–3550	kg/m ³
Heat conductivity of accumulation material	2.3–30	W/(m·K)
Specific heat capacity (basalt, 293 K–573 K)	$-0.0013 \cdot T^2 + 1.894 \cdot T + 312.3$	J/(kg·K)
Heat conductivity (basalt, 293 K–373 K)	$0.0012 \cdot T + 1.93$	W/(m·K)

Fig. 5. Comparison of experimental and numerical results for: (a) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.062$ kg/s, $T_{in}^c = 351.15$ K, (b) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.079$ kg/s, $T_{in}^c = 352.65$ K.

rock material during the experimental series and summarized results of the numerical analyses for the same measurement points.

The results of the numerical model validation process indicated that a high degree of convergence between the numerical and experimental results was obtained, irrespective of the mass flow, maximum air temperature and initial rock distribution, as well as the ambient temperature. The high accuracy of obtaining a fixed maximum temperature at

the test points, which is important from the research perspective, was also achieved - the discrepancy between the numerical and experimental results does not exceed 1 K. The average RMSE [42] for the verified numerical series was 3.92 % considering the course of the temperature rise on all 10 resistive temperature sensors.

3.2. Experimental study of the time constant of a heat tank

The experimental study of the temperature rise of the rock material by means of heat transfer is characterized by varying inlet air parameters which, as mentioned, is due to the need to heat up the HTF supply pipelines. As part of the experimental study, measurements were carried out for a range of maximum air temperatures from 316 K to 352 K. It should be noted that the average ambient temperature from which the air used in the experimental studies was drawn also varied. The lowest recorded ambient temperature was 286 K and the maximum was 292 K. The experimental studies covered the mass flow range studied, from 0.032 kg/s to 0.084 kg/s according to Table 1.

It should also be noted that measuring the temperature of the rock material along the axis of symmetry of the tank only allows an approximate calculation of the charge level of the TES tank. For the purpose of the calculations, the temperature distribution of the basalt was assumed to be linear between successive resistive temperature sensors. Furthermore, the radial temperature distribution was assumed to be constant. Therefore, numerical series were performed in which time-dependent boundary conditions for temperature and mass flow were implemented, which coincide with the experimental data. Based on the performed experimental and numerical series, a set of TES charging characteristics was obtained, to which the C-factors were fitted according to Equation (3) in order to converge with respect to the tested points. Fig. 6 presents the values of the experimental time at which $\theta = 0.70$ was reached and the value of the time constant calculated using Equation (3) for the obtained experimental series. Fig. 7 presents the corresponding values for the numerical calculations of these experimental series.

As indicated in the Figures, the value of the C-factor was 0.908 for the one-dimensional temperature distribution based on the analysis of the experimental data and 0.941 for the analyses performed numerically. For the specified values of the C-factor, none of the points exceeded the limit of deviation from the linear relationship by ± 0.05 . Based on a direct interpretation of the proposed correlation, it can be concluded that the analysis of the one-dimensional experimental data overestimates the amount of energy accumulated in the volume of the heat tank. It can thus be concluded that the radial temperature distribution of the accumulation material must be incorporated into the numerical calculations in order to achieve a greater degree of accuracy in

Fig. 6. Comparison of the results of the calculated time constant and the time to reach $\theta = 0.70$ during the experiments.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the results of the calculated time constant and the time to reach $\theta = 0.70$ during the numerical investigations with experimental boundary conditions.

the results. Fig. 8 presents selected characteristics of the heat storage tank charge level, together with an indication of the $\tau_{0.70}$ values calculated using Equation (3).

As indicated in Fig. 8(a)–(d) and Figs. 6 and 7 the calculation of the time constant of the heat tank correctly estimates $\theta = 0.70$ over the calculated time and assumes a circular increase in the value of this factor.

The experimental series shown in Fig. 8 (d) has the fastest temperature rise of 14.9 K/min in the first minute of the charging stage and values of 8.4 K/min, 4.8 K/min and 2.9 K/min in the subsequent minutes of the stage. The calculated value of the time constant $\tau_{0.70}$ was 1776 s and the value $\theta = 0.70$ calculated from the basalt temperature distribution was reached after 1721 s of the tank charging stage. The theoretical linear function of the increment in the charge level of the heat

storage tank juxtaposed with the actual increment in this value achieved a fit of $RMSE = 3.98\%$. When the time $\tau_{0.70}$ was reached, the discharge temperature of the heat storage tank was 25.97 % of the maximum charge temperature, representing an increase in outlet air temperature of 11.2 K. The experimental series shown in Fig. 8 (c) is characterized by the least intense inlet temperature rise equal to a maximum of 5.1 K/min in the initial part of the charging stage. This is the result of the lowest determined mass flow of air, which also results in a value of $\tau_{0.70} = 4523$ s. The fitted linear function achieved a fit of 3.59 %. When the TES tank charge level $\theta = 0.70$ was reached, the tank outlet air temperature represented 16.8 % of the maximum charge temperature value, which was an increase of 4.3 K relative to the initial temperature. Fig. 9 shows a comparison of the air pressure drop Δp results obtained during the experiment and using the proposed methodology for determining the HTF pressure drop value Δp from the $\theta(t)$ run according to Equations (3), (4) and (6).

As indicated in Fig. 9(a)–(d), the proposed methodology correctly estimates the value of the air pressure drop obtained during the experimental tests. In areas of stabilized flow, the difference between the calculated and experimental results does not exceed 200 Pa. The pressure drop varies in time due to changes in the flow conditions. It was proportional to the mass flow rate, which can be concluded when comparing four different values of this parameter. In each case, at the beginning of the charging phase, the pressure drop decreased, before stabilizing on a given level. It was due to the fact that the fluid temperature was rapidly decreasing when the accumulation material had an initial low temperature. A low temperature of HTF resulted in an increase in density which in turn decreased the fluid velocity. Since the pressure drop is proportional to the square of velocity, it was possible to observe these changes in this initial stage of the charging phase. When the temperature level is stabilized, pressure drop reached its plateau until the end of the charging phase.

A summary of the experimental study indicated that the fit of the linear functions determined from the time constant calculated from

Fig. 8. Comparison of TES tank charge level values during experiments and calculated time constant. (a) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.063$ kg/s, $T_{in}^c = 335.25$ K, (b) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.047$ kg/s, $T_{in}^c = 334.05$ K, (c) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.031$ kg/s, $T_{in}^c = 316.85$ K, (d) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.080$ kg/s, $T_{in}^c = 336.05$ K.

Fig. 9. Comparison of air pressure drop Δp values for experimental data and modelling results according to the proposed methodology: (a) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.063 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 335.25 \text{ K}$, (b) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.047 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 334.05 \text{ K}$, (c) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.031 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 316.85 \text{ K}$, (d) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.080 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 336.05 \text{ K}$.

Equation (3) to the actual charge level runs averaged 4.32% RMSE for the one-dimensional temperature distribution obtained from the experimental study and 4.54% RMSE for the numerical study including the experimental simulation boundary conditions. This therefore indicates both the correct determination of the $\theta = 0.70$ value by means of the proposed correlation on the time constant of the heat tank, and also the correct assumption of a linear increase in the filling of the heat tank over a given time.

3.3. Multivariate numerical study of the time constant of a heat tank

The main assumption of the multivariate analysis was to prove the utility of the proposed methodology based on the theory of the time constant of the heat storage tank in terms of the variable parameters on which the correlation to the time constant according to Equation (3) depended. Experimentally, the consistency of the correlation has been proven for the variable parameters of mass flow of air and maximum inlet air temperature to the heat storage tank. Within the framework of this section, calculations were carried out for 57 heat tank variants according to the assumptions presented in Tables 1 and 2 Both mass flow and inlet air temperature were assumed to be constant throughout the charging stage. Fig. 10 presents the values of the time at which the value $\theta = 0.70$ was reached and the value of the time constant calculated using Equation (3) for the numerical series obtained.

The highest convergence was obtained for a coefficient value of $C = 0.782$ from Equation (3). The difference between the experimental coefficient equal to $C = 0.908$ for the one-dimensional temperature distribution and $C = 0.941$ for the experimental boundary conditions in the numerical simulations indicates the range of applicability of the proposed correlation depending on the rate at which the maximum expected inlet air parameters are obtained. Within the multivariate analysis carried out, no deviation of values greater than $\pm 5\%$ was found for any of the numerical runs carried out. The average RMSE value for the assumed linear run between $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = 0.70$ and the actual θ

Fig. 10. Comparison of the results of the calculated time constant and the time to reach $\theta = 0.70$ during the numerical investigations.

overshoot during the charging stage was 3.02 % with a maximum RMSE = 4.51%. The maximum value of $\tau_{0.70}$ was 6227 s and the value of $\theta = 0.70$ was reached at 6455 for the same numerical series. The minimum value of $\tau_{0.70}$ was 876 s and the $\theta = 0.70$ value during the numerical series was reached at time 919 s. It has been numerically demonstrated that the proposed methodology for estimating the specific charge level of a heat storage tank during the charging stage can be applied to a wide range of porous bed heat storage tank configurations.

As part of the numerical analysis, the charging and discharging processes of the heat storage tank were simulated. It was shown that when keeping the length of the charging and discharging stages equal to $\tau_{0.70}$, the energy efficiency was around 80 %. As the duration of the stages increased, the energy efficiency increased – for $1.2 \cdot \tau_{0.70}$ the efficiency was 83.5 % and for $1.4 \cdot \tau_{0.70}$ it was 87.2 %. However, the

increasing energy efficiency value was due to its definition - the lengthening of the discharge stage allowed deeper cooling of the heat tank with a significant increase in the exhaust loss during the heat tank charging stage. The low energy efficiency for the duration of the charge and discharge stages equal to $\tau_{0.70}$ was therefore not due to increased heat loss to the environment, but to residual heat remaining in the heat accumulator volume.

3.4. Application of time constant in assessment of working conditions of heat storage tank

The determination of the time constant of a heat storage tank with a porous bed and defined design parameters not only makes it possible to determine the conventional linear charging termination of this tank, but can also be used to determine charge level at any time of operation. The determination of the course of the degree of charge is possible by using the function presented in Equation (4). This equation requires the definition of three coefficients: α , β , γ . These coefficients were determined as a function of the time constant of a given heat tank. The values these coefficients are shown in Fig. 11, 12 and 13.

It can be seen that the α , β , γ coefficients are strictly related to values of time constant of the heat tank (see Fig. 11, 12 and 13). Least squares method yielded the following formulas for these coefficients:

$$\frac{\alpha}{\tau_{0.70}} = 0.9688 \cdot \tau_{0.70}^{-0.9989} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\beta}{\tau_{0.70}} = 34.075 \cdot \tau_{0.70}^{-2.6545} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\gamma}{\tau_{0.70}} = 0.7659 \cdot \tau_{0.70}^{-0.9443} \quad (15)$$

On the basis of the Equation (4) it is possible to determine the course of the charge level. The correlations for the coefficients and the charging curves were determined analytically and compared with the previously obtained experimental and numerical results. Fig. 14(a)–(b) show the results for the one-dimensional temperature distribution of the rock material obtained from experiments. Fig. 14(c)–(d) show results for numerical studies with experimental boundary conditions. Fig. 14(e)–(f) show results for numerical tests from a multivariate analysis with fixed inlet air parameters.

The performed tests showed high agreement of the prediction of the $\theta(t)$ course using the presented methodology in relation to the experimental and numerical results. The results maintain high convergence for variable maximum inlet air temperatures and mass flow values, as well as variable tank geometry and accumulation material. The study showed that the Equations (3) and (4) acceptably describes the course of $\theta(t)$

Fig. 11. Dependence of coefficient α based on all experimental and numerical series.

Fig. 12. Dependence of coefficient β based on all experimental and numerical series.

Fig. 13. Dependence of coefficient γ based on all experimental and numerical series.

during the charging stage up to the limit $\tau_{0.70} = 6500$ seconds. Above this value, the deviation of the $\tau_{0.70}$ value and the course of the function occurs. Due to the relatively low temperature and mass flow of the HTF adopted during the experimental and numerical studies, available literature results were used to verify the proposed methodology. The studies used for verification were characterised by higher mass flow of air and its temperature, as well as other accumulation materials. Experimental data available in the literature were also used to validate the method. In the [24] study, the numerical time of the adiabatic charging stage of the CAES system was 28800 s (8 h). According to the assumptions, a mass flow rate of 60.3 kg/s and a maximum air temperature of 773.15 K were used. The porous-filled TES tank had an internal diameter of 5 m and a total length of 70 m, divided into 10-m sections. The calculated $\tau_{0.70}$ value for this tank variant was 24635 s. The results indicated that, at the end of the charging stage, the value of the charge level θ was around 0.80, confirming convergence with the methodology presented. Cascetta et al. [22] used a heat tank 1.8 m high and 0.58 m in diameter filled with alumina in their experimental study. The air flow rate of 0.2 kg/s reached a maximum charging temperature of 300 °C. In the experimental studies discussed in this paper, the same attribute of the laboratory stand was indicated - a delay in achieving the expected inlet air temperature due to heat loss. Therefore, the experimental C factor shown in Fig. 6 was used in the calculation of $\tau_{0.70}$ from Equation (3) to validate the proposed model. The value of the time constant $\tau_{0.70}$ is equal to 4002 s for these input data. According to the authors, during the 4000 s duration of the charging stage, the value of

Fig. 14. Comparison of the charge level course $Q(t)$ using the proposed methodology and (a), (b) experimental results, (c), (d) numerical results with experimental boundary conditions, (e), (f) numerical results. (a) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.047 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 334.05 \text{ K}$, (b) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.063 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 335.25 \text{ K}$, (c) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.047 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 334.05 \text{ K}$, (d) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.063 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 335.25 \text{ K}$, (e) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.070 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 370.15 \text{ K}$, (f) $\dot{m}_{HTF} = 0.070 \text{ kg/s}$, $T_{in}^c = 370.15 \text{ K}$.

the charge level is about 0.73, confirming that the elaborated methodology for determining the time constant of the heat tank is correct. The verification of the proposed methodology, taking into account the results of other studies with a wide HTF temperature range and TES configuration, demonstrates a high level of agreement between the methodology and the results of the charge level during tank operation.

The use of a porous bed heat storage tank results in an optimum solution from the perspective of exergy efficiency, i.e. preserving the energy potential of the heat received, by using a bidirectional flow of heat transfer fluid. During the charging stage, a temperature gradient is observed with a maximum temperature of the storage material near the hot air inlet and a lower temperature towards the tank outlet. In the case of a synchronous tank, i.e. one in which the amount of heat transfer fluid during the charge and discharge stages is the same, residual heat is observed after the discharge stage. This is a consequence of the finite surface area and heat transfer time between the HTF and the rock ma-

terial, as well as the decreasing heat transfer flow over time. As a consequence, the heat tank during cyclic, continuous operation operates in a different degree-of-charge framework to that of the initial start-up. Determining the course of the degree of charge of the tank during cyclic operation is possible based on the following methodology (see Fig. 15).

- Determine the value of $\tau_{0.70}$ from the assumed characteristic quantities of the TES tank and determine the course of $\theta(t)$ during the charging stage of the first tank cycle. This course $\theta(t)_{c,ref}$ is also the reference course for subsequent charging cycles
- Assume a cyclic change in the discharge level of the synchronous heat storage tank. Numerical tests indicated that the behavior of the tank operation during the time constant $\tau_{0.70}$ yields a minimum tank charge level during the discharge stage equal to 0.10 ± 0.01 in the first cycle, 0.14 ± 0.01 in the second cycle, 0.15 ± 0.01 in the third cycle until it settles at 0.16 ± 0.01 for subsequent cycles. It is possible

Fig. 15. Methodology for determining the cyclic operation of a heat tank with indication of characteristic values.

to assume that during the discharge stage the waveform $\theta(t)$ is linear with the operating regime defined by the value of the time constant $\tau_{0.70}$.

- Read from the tank charging course $\theta(t)$ of the first cycle (reference $\theta(t)$ course) time $t_{\min i}$ after the assumed value of the minimum charge level is reached during the discharge stage.
- Plot the next charging cycle curve with $\theta(\tau_{0.70 i} - t_{\min i-1}) = 0$, whereby the theoretical length of this stage must be extended by the value $t_{\min i-1}$. The actual characteristic of the charging stage in cycle i starts at the intersection of the course of the function $\theta(t)_{c i}$ with the course of the charging function $\theta(t)_{d i-1}$ and continues according to the designated time $\tau_{0.70}$.

Based on the analytical model presented, calculations were made of the heat storage tank's charge rate during cyclic operation, where the charging and discharging times were equal to the value of the time constant $\tau_{0.70}$ for the given tank configuration, and compared with numerical results for the same case. The results of the cyclic operation of

the heat storage tank using the analytical model are shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16 shows the operation of the thermal storage tank for 10 complete cycles, where synchronized charging and discharging took place. In the discharging stage, the inlet and outlet were reversed. According to the methodology of the TES tank analytical model, a theoretical extension of the charging stage was assumed (dashed line). Due to the higher charge level achieved in successive cycles (up to $\theta = 0.786$), the numerical decrease in charge level approaches repeatability. Therefore, better agreement between the analytical and numerical solutions were observed. The numerical calculations also have proven that there is repeatability in the obtained air outlet temperatures during the stages, and the increase in temperature values has a similar character to the increase in θ_{\max} in successive cycles.

4. Summary

This paper proposes a methodology to analyze the performance of a porous-filled TES tank based on time constant theory. Experimental and numerical results have proven the broad applicability of the proposed analytical model. A multivariate numerical analysis was performed to check the accuracy of the obtained $\tau_{0.70}$ and $\theta(t)$ values for a wide range of TES tank and HTF characteristic data. The analytical model also showed agreement for significantly different values of temperature and HTF flux, which was obtained by validation with the results of other authors' studies. Based on the analyses performed, it was found that:

- The proposed formula for the time constant of a porous bed heat tank

$$\frac{\tau_{0.70}}{V} = C \cdot \frac{\rho_{\text{bed}}}{m_f} \left(\frac{c_p}{\alpha} \right)$$

acceptably determines the point at which the heat tank is 70 % filled with heat relative to its maximum capacity for the defined boundary conditions of the heat transfer system.

- The value of the C -coefficient closely depends on the directness of the heat transfer fluid to reach its nominal flow conditions and maximum temperature. The C -value determines the amount of theoretical energy surplus that must be incurred for the tank to reach a charge level of 70 %.
- The proposed formula for determining the course of the heat tank charge level $\theta(t) = \alpha \cdot \frac{e^{\beta \cdot t} - e^{-\beta \cdot t}}{e^{\beta \cdot t} + e^{-\beta \cdot t}} = \alpha \cdot \tanh(\beta \cdot t)$ accurately determines both the course of the heat tank charge level and the point where $\theta = 0.70$ is reached and its maximum value during the charging stage.

Fig. 16. Results of using the proposed analytical model methodology to determine the cyclic operation of the Thermal Energy Storage and its charge level θ .

The applicability of the formula has been confirmed both experimentally and numerically. The dependence of the α , β , γ coefficients on the value of $\tau_{0.70}$ obtained with the proposed correlation has been proven.

- The proposed methodology for determining $\theta(t)$ during cyclic operation of the TES tank satisfactorily reproduces the values achieved during numerical analyses. The applicability of the indicated methodology has been confirmed up to the limit $\tau_{0.70} = 6500$ s. It has been also proven that the achieved θ values during cyclic operation closely depend on the calculated $\tau_{0.70}$ value.
- The proposed methodology can extend the analytical models of heat storage tank systems used so far. In addition, the proposed correlation for time constant can provide a decision-making tool for the initial design process of a heat storage tank subjected to cyclic charging and discharging.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jakub Ochmann: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Krzysztof Rusin:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Michał Jurczyk:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Sebastian Rulik:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Łukasz Bartela:** Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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